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Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Competency and Administrators' Job Performance Effectiveness in Institutions of Higher learning in Delta State of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The world has become a global suburb as a result of the Internet-computer actuated information and communication technology (ICT). Administrators of institutions in advanced education systems have taken advantage of ICT for enhanced administrative job performance effectiveness. This study investigated ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The population of the study comprised of 722 administrative heads of the twelve (12) public federal and state institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The entire population of 722 respondents were chosen as sample for the study using the census sampling technique. Three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Instruments for data collection consisted administrators' job performance effectiveness questionnaire (AJPEQ) and ICT competency questionnaire (ICTCQ, which used the 4-point Likert scale. Experts in education research ascertained the face validity of the instruments, and the content and construct validities of the instruments were assessed with confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) statistical tool. The reliability of AJPEQ and ICTCQ were found to have Cronbach alpha (α) reliability indexes of .92 and .86 respectively. Pearson's product moment correlation (PPMC) coefficient, r and linear regression analysis were used to test hypotheses at .05 level of statistical significance. Findings of the study revealed that ICT competency seriously positively affected administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. It was recommended that if administrators of educational institutions must overcome the numerous challenges in our institutions of higher learning; ranging from cultism, truancy, impersonation, poor academic achievements, to forgery of tuition fee receipts and transform the entire education system, both tertiary and secondary schools' administrators must not only be professionally qualified, they should be given constant training and retaining through workshops/conferences on the effective use of ICT tools for them to acquire adequate ICT competency to tackle the numerous challenges that beset them while performing their administrative tasks among others.

Keywords: Information and communication technology-ICT; ICT competency; administrators; job performance effectiveness; institutions of higher learning

INTRODUCTION

Effective job performance among school administrators presupposes information and communication technology (ICT) usage in the twenty first century's education institutions of higher learning. This belief is occasioned by the happenings in the schooling system. At the tertiary level of education, it is assumed that the moral decomposition of society can be cured. However, this assumption was not the case because the acquisition of knowledge, irrespective of the level of school attained, reveals that the establishment of more institutions of higher learning to meet the demand for higher education only meets the extrinsic values, rather than the intrinsic values of education. In spite of this, education is still a dependable vehicle through which people are positively transformed to create a highly skilled and competent workforce that would bring about necessary change and modification in the nature of man to establish egalitarian society. Therefore, administrators' effectiveness is a required important resource in this regard. Administrators' effectiveness connotes ability for administrators and other workers produce outcomes related to the objectives of their organization or institution.

Higher education (also tertiary education) broadly refers to post-secondary education- it is post-basic education in institutions such as Universities, all inter University centres such as Nigeria French Language Village, Nigeria Arabic Language Village, National Institute of Nigerian Languages, institutions such as Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs) and Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics, and other specialized institutions such as Colleges of Agriculture, School of Nursing, School of Midwifery, Schools of Health and Technology and the National Teachers' Institutes (NTI) (FRN, 2014). While administrator's effectiveness connotes the degree to which administrator and other workers produce outcomes related to the objectives of their organisation or institution.

However, it is believed that to salvage the image of our institutions of higher learning and transform the entire education system, the school administrators must not only be professionally qualified with extensive work experience, they need adequate ICT competency to tackle the numerous challenges that beset the education sector. Consequently, there has been an active lobby within and outside the educational sector to advocate for ICT competency for improved job performance and effective administration in modern education institutions of higher learning.

The conception of ICT in education is anchored on four fundamental characteristics: (1.) ICT is an object- which means that one can learn about ICT; (2.) ICT is a framework for information creation, processing and transmission; (3.) ICT is an instructional tool which assists teachers in teaching and students in learning; (4.) ICT is a management tool which can help administrators perform their tasks effectively in their organisations or institutions (Omoghenemuko, 2024). Although the four concept of ICT in education are important in this research, the fourth concept of ICT that talks about ICT as a tool for organization for administrative management in institutions is most important and the crux of this research.

ICT is an integration of science and technology that includes the full range of computer hardware and software, telecommunication, computer networks and mobile smart phones, the Internet and Web, wired and wireless networks, digital systems, projector and screen, loud speakers, radio and television, robotics, and video cameras, and so on required for collection and processing of data (texts, video, audio, pictures), and generating information, and the storing and disseminating of information through the information superhigh-way- the Internet; to different users in a specified format for decision making (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

ICT is ubiquitous and driven by computers. Life these days is significantly dependent on a person's competence in ICT usage and without ICT skills one may be regarded as functionally illiterate in the 21st century (Omoghenemuko, 2024). Administrators have to recognize their responsibility to the general public and develop a professional outlook and attitude to others to create and maintain a safe, healthy and reliable work and information society through ICT application to all sphere of human specialisation or professionalism and administration.

Information and communication technology-ICT offers numerous opportunities for changes in various school-related processes like school administrative management, teaching and learning. School administrators with different management styles need modification to integrate ICT usage; following emergence of computer networking and Internet requiring school administrators to use computers as a management and administrative tool (Makhanu & Kamper, 2012). Schools should take advantage of these opportunities to introduce drastic changes in education infrastructure, improve skills needed by teachers and administrators to manage education institutions. ICT provides veritable tools for the management of an institution, including professionalism. ICT helps in overall school effectiveness improvement. ICT-driven schools or academies are suitably referred to as 'Smart schools or academies' today because of ICT-provision for administrators to enhance their administrative support for teachers' efficacy and improved students' learning outcomes (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

It is therefore evident that, for any nation to compete favourably with advanced economies in the world, that nation must develop the computing knowledge and skills of its citizenry. Today, ICT which is a branch of study in computer science, is the major driver of global knowledge economy. Undoubtedly, ICT, which is the combination of computers and other data/information processing systems, telecommunication, Internet, broadcasting, multimedia and other associated technologies has promised essential change and innovation in education management within a short time and has become indispensable tool in modern school administrative management efficiency and effectiveness (Omoghenemuko, 2024).

The fact remains that most school administrators in tertiary institutions, though are vast in their specific fields of studies, lack the required administrative skill and ICT competencies. ICT competency for improved job performance and effective administration in previous studies revealed it was a significant correlate of job performance and effectiveness in the administration of tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Koko & Ngulube, 2021; Nkang & Uwah, 2020; Amadi & Otamiri, 2020; Kayode et al., 2019).

LITERATURE REVIEW

For instance, Kabiru and John (2013) examined the competence of ICT in rural and urban secondary school ICT teachers for the implementation of ICT curriculum in North Eastern Nigeria, and found that the competence of ICT teachers on policy, curriculum, pedagogy, technology, administration and professional development is low. Obstacles to ICT teachers' competences were identified as lack of hardware, software, and financial resources, lack of electricity in most rural schools and insufficient information and experience from teachers in ICT applications. The finding from this study was however, consistent with those from Hennessy et al. (2010) and Hapman and Malilick (2013) who focused on subject knowledge to explicitly include 21st century skills that are needed to construct new knowledge and engage in lifelong learning. It was discovered from their research that the ability to collaborate, communicate, create, innovate and think critically are vital in ICT Curriculum implementation and that successful curriculum implementation of ICT depends on the knowledge and skills of ICT teachers to structure their leaning. In a study by Omoghenemuko (2024) on the effect of computer usage on the job performance effectiveness of school administrators and teachers' job performance effectiveness in private secondary schools in Warri South local government area of Delta state, Nigeria, it was discovered that competency in computer usage, which is a major component of ICT substantially influenced administrators and teachers' job performance effectiveness in private secondary schools in Warri South local government area of Delta state.

Statement of the Problem

Several challenges are known to undermine effective job performance of administrators in institutions of higher learning in Nigeria. Most Nigeria public schools are not known to be headed by administrators with adequate ICT competency. There is also doubt that ill-trained educational administrators in Nigeria public schools have adequate administrators' ICT competency that can enhance their job performance effectiveness. To the larger society, it is believed that the overall standard of education is falling because of the continuous poor academic performance evident in exponential low grades in courses among tertiary institutions' undergraduates in Nigeria.

The Nigeria society also have the notion that institutions of higher learnings' administrators, lack the basic knowledge and competencies for dealing with the problems of vandalism, cultism, hooliganism, high school dropout rate, examination malpractice, truancy, among others. In effect, the effectiveness of the administrators of institutions of higher learning is questioned. Consequently, there has been an active lobby within and outside the educational sector to advocate for ICT competency for improved job performance and effective administration in modern higher education institutions learning in advanced education system across the globe. Therefore, the statement of the problem of the study, was: Would ICT competency improve administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State of Nigeria?

Conceptual framework

Figure 1 Conceptual framework or model of the study

Figure 1 is the conceptual framework or model of the study. It shows the relationship between information and communication technology-ICT competency (independent variable) and administrators' job performance effectiveness (dependent variable) in institutions of higher learning in Delta State of Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide and direct the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between extent of ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.
2. There is no significant relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.
3. There is no significant effect of the relationship between ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to assess the characteristics of ICT competency as predictors of administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine the extent of relationship of ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Delta State.
2. Determine the relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.
3. Determine the effect of predictor characteristics of ICT competency on administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

Significance of the Study

This study would serve as a veritable guide for both federal and state Ministries of Education charged with the responsibility of planning, organizing, and coordinating the affairs of education in Nigeria in general and in Delta State in particular.

The study would provide umbrella bodies such as the National University Commission (NUC), the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) and National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE), insight into the operations of school organisation and administration by administrators and how to check and correct the anomalies of their excesses in terms of their ICT competency and their administrators' job performance level.

Educational administrators, planners, policy makers and other stakeholders in school business administration would be provided with information necessary to guide and enhance their future endeavour, especially as it relates to their ICT competency and job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Nigeria and the Delta State public tertiary institutions in particular.

Scope of the Study

The study covered information and communication technology (ICT) competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in the twelve (12) institutions of higher learning in Delta State of Nigeria.

METHOD

Design of the Study

The study adopted a correlation survey research design. Because the researchers attempted to find the relationship between ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness. Variables in the study are: ICT competency (independent variable) and administrators' job performance effectiveness (dependent variable).

Population of the Study

The target of population of the study comprised all administrative staff of the twelve (12) public federal and state institutions of higher learning in Delta State with head administrative staff strength of 722 surveyed with an average of 60 administrative heads in each of the institutions.

Sampling and Sampling Technique

The sampling technique adopted in the study is the census or total population sampling technique- a type of purposive technique where the target population is used as sample in a study. The sample for the research was selected from the twelve (12) public institutions of higher learning in Delta State of Nigeria with at least an average of 60 administrative heads in each of the institutions. By implication, a total of 722 administrators were surveyed in the study.

Instrumentation

Two research instruments were used in the study- Administrators’ Job Performance Effectiveness Questionnaire (AJPEQ) and ICT Competency Questionnaire (ICTCQ), all in relation to public institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The instruments used the 4-point Likert scale of strongly agree (SA) (4), agree (A) (3), disagree (D) (2) and strongly disagree (SD) (1) respectively.

Validation of the Instruments

The researchers subjected the instruments to strict and thorough scrutiny through the assistance of three experts in educational research and statistics and measurement and evaluation in the Delta State University, Abraka. The experts ascertained the face validity of the instruments, and the content and construct validities of the instruments were assessed with the use of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) statistical tool. ICTCQ had 75.69% content validity while its construct validity ranged from .51 to .93, and AJPEQ had 79.38% content validity while its construct validity ranged from .50 to .85.

Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability of the instruments used in the study was established using the Cronbach alpha (α) reliability technique in International Business Machine Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS) version 27 on Windows 10. The reliability of the instrument yielded Cronbach alpha (α) reliability index of .86 as a measure of the internal consistency of the ICTCQ, while for AJPEQ, it was found to have Cronbach alpha (α) reliability index of .92, confirming the instruments’ reliability and suitability for the study.

Method of data Analysis

The hypotheses were tested at .05 level of statistical significance using Pearson’s (PPMC) correlation coefficient, r and linear regression analysis.

The study also reported effect sizes, eta squared (η^2) of the results using Cohen’s (1988, 1992) *d* criteria for effect size measurement (Table 1) to establish the practical significance of the results of the study.

Table 1

Effect size benchmark for correlation (Hopkin’s as cited by Kotrilik et al., 2011)

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
	0.90 – 1.00	Nearly, practically, or almost: perfect, distinct, infinite effect size.
	0.70 – 0.90	Very large, very high, huge effect size.
Correlation coefficients	0.50 – 0.69	Large, high, major effect size.
	0.30 – 0.49	Moderate, medium effect size.
	0.10 – 0.29	Small, low, mirror effect size.
	0.00 – 0.10	Tiny, practically zero effect size.

Source: Igwebuik. (2022).

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between extent of ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State

Table 2

Pearson’s correlation result of extent of relationship between ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

Variables	n	Mean	Std. Deviation (SD)	r	P-value	Effect Size Eta squared (η^2)
ICT competency		7.39	.34			
Administrators’ job performance effectiveness	722	7.31	.51	.404**	.001	.68

** Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed)

Pearson’s correlation was carried out to determine the relationship between ICT competency and administrator’s job performance effectiveness as depicted in Table 2. The results indicated that, there was a high extent of positive relationship between ICT competency with (Mean = 7.39, SD = .34) and administrator’s job performance effectiveness with (Mean =7.31, SD. = .51), which was statistically significant (r = .404, n = 722 and p=.001 < .05). The null hypothesis that state that, “there is no significant relationship between ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State” is rejected. This indicates that there is a significant relationship between ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The results imply that an increase in ICT competency resulted in 40.4% increase in administrators’ job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The effect size, eta squared (η^2) value of .68 using Hopkin’s effect size benchmark for correlation cited by Kotrilik et al. (2011), is large (See Table 1), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

Table 3

Pearson correlation result between rate of ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

Variables	n	Mean	Std. Deviation (SD)	r	P-value	Effect Size Eta squared (η^2)
ICT competency		4.67	.74			
Administrators’ job performance effectiveness	722	4.29	.52	.12**	.001	.52

** Correlation is significant at the .01 level (2-tailed)

Table 3 showed the results of Pearson’s correlation carried out to determine whether there was a relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness status, indicated that there was a weak positive relationship between ICT competency with (Mean = 4.67, SD. = .74) and administrator’s job performance effectiveness status with (Mean =4.29, SD. = .52),which was statistically significant (r = .12, n = 722 and p=.001< .05).The null hypothesis that states that, “there is no significant relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State was rejected because the results of analysis indicated that, there was a significant relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators’ job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

The results imply that an increase in the rate of ICT competency would predict an increase in administrators' job performance effectiveness status by 12% in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The effect size, eta squared (η^2) value of .52 using Hopkin's effect size benchmark for correlation cited by Kotrilik et al. (2011), is large (See Table 1), indicating that practical significance of the results is highly supported.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant effect of relationship between ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

Table 4

Pearson correlation result of effect of relationship between ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

Variables	n	Mean	Std. Deviation (SD)	r	P-value	Effect Size Eta squared (η^2)
ICT competency		3.76	.57			
Administrators' job performance effectiveness	722	3.32	.54	.652**	.000	.72

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The results in Table 4 of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation carried out to determine the effect of relationship between ICT competency and administrator's job performance effectiveness indicated that, there was a weak positive relationship between ICT competency with (Mean = 3.76, SD. = .57) and administrator's job performance effectiveness with (Mean = 3.32, SD. = .54), which was statistically significant ($r = .65$, $n = 722$ and $p = .000 < .05$). The null hypothesis stated that, "there is no significant effect of relationship between ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State was rejected since result of computation revealed that, "there is a significant effect of relationship between ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The result implies that an increase in ICT competency will result in 65.2% increase in administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The effect size, eta squared (η^2) value of .72 using Hopkin's effect size benchmark for correlation cited by Kotrilik et al. (2011), is very large (See Table 1), indicating that practical significance of the results is very highly supported.

Table 5

Model summary of ICT competency as predictor of administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State

Model	r	r Square (r^2)	Adjusted r Square (r^2)	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.386 ^a	.082	.271	.327

a. Predictors: (Constant), ICT Competency

Table 6

ANOVA Result of Predictor Characteristics of ICT Competency on Administrators' Job Performance Effectiveness in Institutions of higher learning in Delta State

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.811	1	3.270	40.39	.000 ^b
	Residual	109.809	720	.107		
	Total	119.620	721			

a. Dependent Variable: Administrators' Job Performance Effectiveness

b. Predictors: (Constant), ICT Competency.

Table 7

Regression of Coefficient of Predictor Characteristics of ICT Competency on Administrators' Job Performance Effectiveness in Institutions of higher learning in Delta State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.96	.165		11.076	.000
	ICT competency	.081	.034	.066	2.177	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Administrators' Job Performance Effectiveness

A simple linear regression was calculated to investigate the effect of ICT competency on administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The result of the multiple linear regressions suggests a positively weak and significant effect of ICT competency on administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. This finding was possible because $(F(1, 721) = 30.556, p=.000 < .05)$ with R^2 adjusted of .271 (see Tables 5 and 6). The null hypothesis is rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis. The conclusion reached is that; predictor characteristics of ICT competency have significant effect on administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. In Table 7, the unstandardized slope (1.831), b-coefficient for the independent variable "ICT competency" was .074, indicating a strong positive effect on administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. This implies that higher numeric values for the independent variable of ICT competency" is associated with higher numeric values for the dependent variable "administrators' job performance effectiveness". The r-squared (r^2) adjusted= .271 indicates that only 27.1% of administrators' job performance is caused by ICT competency, while the remaining 82.9% is caused by other factors such as professionalism, work experience, etc., not included in this study. From the simple linear regression general equation that is given by:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \epsilon$$

Where: Y is the dependent variable

X is the independent variable

β_0 is the intercept

β_1 is the slope

ϵ is the error term

The simple linear regression equation generated from this study is given by:

$$Y = 1.96 + .081X + .034$$

Where; Y is administrators' job performance effectiveness (dependent variable), X is ICT competency (independent variable), β_0 is the intercept 1.96, and β_1 is the slope = .081, while ϵ which is the error term = .034

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results generated from the analysis of data collected for this study has provided great insights on how the respondents from all the eighteen institutions of higher learning in Delta State of Nigeria view ICT competency as predictors of administrators' job performance effectiveness. The discussion therefore, proceeds along the lines of the three purposes, accompanied by research questions, hypotheses and their corroboration or disagreement with existing relevant literature.

The result of hypothesis one reveals a significant relationship between extent of ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The result implies that an increase in ICT competency will result in 10.4% increase in administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. This development led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The descriptive analysis indicates that the grand mean of 3.16 is greater than the criterion Mean of 2.5 (ie. 4-point Likert scale average) which indicates agreement that predictor characteristics of ICT competency are related to administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. This implies that the respondents affirmed that the operation of computer / other ICT gadgets (resources), use of e-mail in sending and receiving information or mails, accessing the world wide web (www) effectively, using the web browser to identify Internet and hosts addresses, accessing public voice page and messaging, public radio page, public relay internet

information dissemination, managing records, corporate lease asset files, video conference / mobiles telephone system/ general work flow and handling school administration locally, nationally and internationally are highly related to administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The finding above is not in agreement with the findings of Kabiru and John (2013) that examined the competence of ICT in rural and urban secondary school ICT teachers for the implementation of ICT curriculum in North Eastern Nigeria. Results reveal that the competence of ICT teachers on policy, curriculum, pedagogy, technology, administration and professional development is low. Obstacles to ICT teachers' competences were identified as lack of hardware, software, and financial resources, lack of electricity in most rural schools and insufficient information and experience from teachers in ICT applications. The findings from this study was however, consistent with those from Hennessy et al. (2010) and Hapman and Malilick (2013) who focused on subject knowledge to explicitly include 21st century skills that are needed to construct new knowledge and engage in lifelong learning. It was discovered from their research that the ability to collaborate, communicate, create, innovate and think critically are vital in ICT Curriculum implementation and that successful implementation of ICT curriculum depends on the knowledge and skills of ICT teachers to structure their leaning environment.

The result of hypothesis two reveals a significant relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. This development led to the rejection of the null hypothesis which State that there is no significant relationship between rate of ICT competency and administrators' job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The opinion of the respondents also confirmed the issue as reflected by inferential statistical analysis; the descriptive analysis indicated that the grand Mean of 3.30 is greater than the criterion Mean of 2.5. This implies that the rate of ICT competency is highly related to administrators' job performance effectiveness status in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The result of the rating of staff of the twelve (12) institutions of higher learning in Delta State revealed that there is high correlation between their institutions current principal officers' ICT competency and their job performance effectiveness status. This finding is corroborated by study of Omoghenemuko (2024) on the effect of computer usage on the job performance effectiveness of school administrators and teachers' job performance effectiveness in private secondary schools in Warri South local government area of Delta state, Nigeria. Omoghenemuko's study found that proficiency in computer usage, which is a major component of ICT, substantially influenced administrators and teachers' job performance effectiveness in private secondary schools in Warri South local government area of Delta state.

The results of hypothesis three revealed that predictor characteristics of ICT competency have significant effect on administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. This implies that ICT competency highly affected administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. This finding is consistent with that of Omoghenemuko (2024) on the effect of computer usage on the job performance effectiveness of school administrators and teachers' job performance effectiveness in private secondary schools in Warri South local government area of Delta state, Nigeria. Omoghenemuko's study found that competency in computer usage, which is a major component of ICT, substantially influenced administrators and teachers' job performance effectiveness in private secondary schools in Warri South local government area of Delta state.

CONCLUSION

The main concern of this study was to investigate whether ICT competency was a predictor of administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

The outcome of the study revealed that: extent of administrators' ICT competency and rate of ICT competency were highly correlated with administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. The study also found that ICT competency seriously positively affected administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State. Because the respondents affirmed that the effective operation of the computer/other ICT gadgets (resources), use of WhatsApp and e-mail in sending and receiving information, accessing the world wide web (www) effectively, using the web browser to identify the internet and host address are related to administrators' job performance effectiveness in institutions of higher learning in Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to reap the full benefits of ICT competency for employees' administrative job performance effectiveness, it was recommended that:

1. Management of institutions of higher learning in Delta State should ensure that heads of information and communication technology (ICT) departments of their institutions, embark on exploration of the improvement

in the operation of computers and other ICT gadgets (resources) and organize training workshops for all administrative staff to improve their job performance effectiveness;

2. For administrators of educational institutions to overcome the numerous challenges in our institutions of higher learning; ranging from cultism, truancy, impersonation, poor academic achievements, to forgery of tuition fee receipts and transform the entire education system, both tertiary and secondary schools' administrators must not only be professionally qualified, they should be given constant training and retaining through workshops/conferences on ICT usage, for them to acquire adequate ICT competency to tackle the numerous challenges that beset the education sector.

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